

Impact of broadband on employment

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1 Introduction

Broadband technology has significantly changed the way people work. It has affected all aspects of modern human life. People use broadband for various purposes. Matching and search of a job have been much easier with the evolution of broadband. The potential employer and employee can find each other with significantly less time and effort. Broadband and ICTs are transforming classical forms of handling business. They are permitting speedy advancement in e-business and promoting reduced trade costs, improves market information, open market connection, comes to a larger chain of consumers and engages in international value chains, while providing unique spaces for employment, education and skill development.

In this chapter, we examine how accessibility of broadband affects the labor market in different countries. In addition to measuring the effects of broadband deployment on labor market outcomes, we investigate how these effects vary with the income level of countries. The differential effect of broadband in various income countries will have significant policy implications. Broadband technology can assist isolated markets by opening new business and employment opportunities, providing such rural and isolated areas to integrate with the rest of the national market for goods and labor.

The broadband diffusion started to around the developed world in the late

1990s. By the year 2000, almost half of the population in the US was obtaining information through the Internet. However, across most of the world, the Internet had not yet had considerable influence, only 7% in the East Asia and Pacific region and 1% in South Asia and in Sub-Saharan Africa were using the Internet. 16 years later, in 2016, three-quarters (76%) of people in the US were online, and during these years' states from many parts of the world seized up: in Malaysia 79% used the Internet; in Spain and Singapore 81%; in France 86%; in South Korea and Japan 93%; in Denmark and Norway 97%; and Iceland tops the ranking with 98% of the population online(Roser et al. 2020).

Estimates obtained from country, and year fixed effects in this study indicate that gaining full access to broadband is associated with 1.71 percentage points increase in the employment of the working-age population in low-income countries while that is 1.63 percentage for high-income countries. The benefit of broadband access is exploited highest in middle-income countries where higher GDP growth rate is supposed to create more job opportunities. We carefully analyzed whether the increase in employment is due to increase in labor force and rise in the number of employers. The empirical evidence we obtained suggests that employment is rising at(2.79% points) higher rate than labor force(almost 0) proving our claim that employment is driven by broad-

band penetration. This conclusion is robust to various income group countries.

The investment in broadband diffusion around the world is in the rise every day. The U.S. presently allocates about \$10 billion annually subsidizing broadband service, about \$5 billion of which reaches precisely to rural areas. The government of Canada is spending \$1.7 billion in new funding for broadband infrastructure. This includes a new Universal Broadband Fund to support broadband projects across the country. It is also supporting broadband projects through the \$2 billion Rural and Northern Stream of the Investing in Canada Infrastructure Program.

Estimates obtained from OLS are likely to be biased and there might be endogeneity problem where some unobserved factors can be affecting broadband and labor market outcomes simultaneously. Furthermore, the places with higher income can attract broadband providers in that area, causing reverse causality. We addressed endogeneity issue in two ways: First we employ country fixed effects model that eliminates unobserved heterogeneity across the countries. Second, we analyze the timing of broadband access and find that there is no reverse causality present. In the same way, to address the second part, whether employment is increasing due to increase in the number of employers in the country, we run country and time fixed effect regression and found that moving from no broadband to full coverage, yields 4.71% points in-

crease in the number of employers while employees per employer are increased by 6.7% points. This further proves that broadband access is contributing to increase employment.

We test for the skill-biased technological innovation model, which explores how information technologies influence labor demand. The core prediction of that design is that if broadband technology is interdependent to labor market skills, then we should see greater effects among higher trained employees. The effect should be small for unskilled workers. We find evidence that conclusions are coherent with the skill-biased technological change model. The results from fixed effect regression depict that if broadband access is increased by 100 percentage points, there is an increase in employment of workers having advanced college degree by 4.02 percentage points. The broadband coefficient is insignificant but positive in case of workers with an intermediate degree. In the case of workers only having basic education, every 100-percentage increase in broadband access decreases the employment opportunity by 1.29 percentage points. These results are consistent with the theory that broadband adoption increases firm's demand for skilled labors but decreases the demand for unskilled workers.

The paper proceeds as follows: The next section briefly reviews the related literature. In Section 3, we discuss the data and descriptive statistics. Section

4 presents the econometric model, section 5 presents result, section 6 shows the causality and Section 7 concludes.

2 Literature Review

Atasoy (2013) analyzes the effects of the expansion of broadband Internet access from 1999 to 2007 on labor market outcomes throughout the United States. Using models that include country and time fixed effects, the author finds that gaining access to broadband services in a county is associated with approximately a 1.8 percentage point increase in the employment rate, with larger effects in rural and isolated areas. Akerman et al. (2015) by employing Norwegian data suggest that broadband Internet improves the labor-market outcomes and productivity of skilled workers but worsens that for unskilled workers. Dettling (2017) investigates how rapid home Internet use has affected labor supply. She finds that exogenously determined high-speed Internet use leads to a 4.1 percentage point increase in labor-force participation for married women. Khorshed and Khan (2017) examine the causal effect of household access to broadband Internet on individuals' labour market outcomes in an Australian rural and regional context and found that the causal effect of household access to broadband Internet on individuals' labour force outcomes is not statistically significant. Wang et al.(2018) by using the

difference-in-differences estimates in Chinese's context, show that the deployment of high-quality broadband promotes regional employment, especially employment in the skilled service sector. The positive effect is larger in cities with better developed tertiary industry and more educated residents. Hounghonon and Liang(2018), using a fuzzy difference-in-difference estimation strategy for French data, find that broadband internet destroys jobs, although the unemployment rate seems not to be affected. Stockinger(2019) investigates the effect of broadband Internet availability on German establishments' employment growth, and the findings suggest that broadband expansion has helped create jobs in firms, which use broadband intensely. Nakyung and Lee(2019) examine the effect of the broadband use on disabled employment in the United States during 2013–2016 using a county-level panel data set and found that, on average, broadband use increases the disabled employment.

3 Data

Our sample consist of 190 countries on the earth between 2000 and 2017 obtained from two different sources. Data on employment related variables are from the International Labor Organization Statistics(ILO-STAT). The data on all other variables is sourced from the development indicator of the World Bank. We matched both data-sets to form our sample.we employ data on

broadband subscription per hundred of the people in the country. Similarly, data on employment is taken as percentage of total working-age population, education achievement by diverse age groups and gender, population density per square kilometer and gross national income per capita .

Table 1 presents the main descriptive statistics for each variables. Our main variable is broadband. It is defined as the percentage of people in a country with access to broadband. The mean vale for broadband is 7.93 indicating that in an average almost 8 out of 100 people have access to broadband. There is large variation in broadband access across the countries as maximum is 63.88 and minimum is 0.00002. The least number of broadband access per hundred people is 0.00002, which is Tonga in the year. In the same way, fixed telephone per hundred has minimum value 0.0004 for St. Martin for the year. Data on different education level are taken as a percentage of people at least completed particular level of study. For example, 5.17 percentage of people has completed primary level schooling in Cambodia in 2007. Lowest percentage(0.8) of people completed bachelor's degree in Burundi in 2014, and percentage of people completed MS degree in Kosovo is 0.1 in 2009. Population density is taken as people residing in per square kilometers. Number of employers in a country is given in terms of per thousand, minimums of one thousand employers are there in Djibouti in 2008.

Table 1: Summary statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Broadband	3312	7.93	11.15	0.00002	63.88
Telephone	3280	20	20.2	0.00044	132.72
Mobile-cellular	3245	69.69	50.01	0.019	328.8
Primary	763	82.28	20.04	5.17	100
Lower secondary	840	67.16	24.92	2.04	100
Secondary	2364	76.98	29.11	6.11	100
Post-secondary(%)	832	22.89	13.04	0.27	69.07
Population with BS degree(%)	233	15.53	8.89	0.8	36.95
Population with MS degree(%)	185	6.04	5.84	0.12	28.15
Population density	4674	350.09	1686.95	.14	21389.1
Population age 0-14	3126	4.81e+07	1.61e+08	18872	1.46e+09
Population age 15-65	3126	62.53	6.94	47.33	85.87
Population age 65+	3126	9517210	3.56e+07	2802	4.18e+08
GNI per capita	4250	11178.93	16757.8	110	120490
GDP per capita(USD)	3228	13716.95	21153.75	111.93	189170.9
Number of Employers(thousands)	1892	440.38	768.3	1	7240
Number of Employees(thousands)	2020	10612.08	43308.7	2	697880
Employee per employer	1876	28.01	111.36	.14	4559
Employment to pop. ratio, (%)	3024	57.14	11.56	28.84	87.82
Employment to pop. ratio, female (%)	2232	44.94	14.04	4.46	93
Employment in industry, male	4194	24.64	9.92	3.15	67.63
Employment in services	4194	50.46	18.54	5.38	88.02
Employment in services, female	4194	57.89	25.44	2.47	98.67
Employment in services, male	4194	45.34	14.9	8.54	82.71
Employment in agriculture, male	4194	30.02	22.27	.09	87.93
Employment in agriculture	4194	29.72	23.6	.06	92.55
Unemployed with advanced degree	1,602	6.32	5.06	.045	46.03
Unemployed with Intermediate	1,578	7.70	7.34	.44	65.09
Unemployment with basic education	1,584	5.48	4.00	.057	35.24
Unemployment without basic education	1,598	12.45	8.61	.065	65.58
Unemployment (unspecified education)	1,606	11.74	8.42	.12	54.89

Table (2) presents the correlation matrix. It shows that broadband and mobile-cellular are positively correlated with employment ratio. The correlation matrix, however, is limited in the information it provides. This is because pairwise correlations fail to address simultaneity due to omitted variables. For example, the negative correlation between employment ratio and mobile-

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

(1)

	Employment Ratio	Broadband	Telephone	Mobilecelluar	pop. age15-65	pop. age 65 plus	secondaryenrl	pop density	GDP per capita
Employment Ratio	1								
Broadband	0.0676**	1							
Telephone	0.165***	0.690***	1						
Mobilecelluar	-0.0976***	0.639***	0.502***	1					
pop. age 15-65	0.202***	0.457***	0.593***	0.592***	1				
pop. age 65 plus	0.0360	-0.0266	-0.0493*	-0.0447*	0.0726***	1			
Secondaryenrl	0.317***	0.631***	0.744***	0.614***	0.733***	-0.0500*	1		
Pop. Density	0.0728***	0.169***	0.145***	0.287***	0.250***	-0.0378	0.0627**	1	
GDP per capita	0.0679*	0.761***	0.690***	0.554***	0.468***	-0.0633**	0.579***	0.219***	1

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

cellular is biased when there is third variable affecting both employment ratio and mobile-cellular concurrently.

4 Empirical Specification

In this section, we present the model specification. We start with the ordinary least squares.

OLS specification is as follows:

$$ER_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i + \delta m_i + \epsilon_i \tag{1}$$

Where, ER is the log of the employment ratio, x , variable of interest, is broadband subscription per 100 people, m = set of control variables in log terms: fixed telephone subscription per 100, mobile cellular per 100, population density, income and demographic variables.

Our empirical specification exploits the panel structure of the data: country fixed effects absorb any permanent heterogeneity at the country level. Time fixed effects absorb time-specific shocks and trends that are shared by all locations. We model the employment-to- working-age population ratio in a

county i at time t as:

$$ER_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{it} + \delta M_{it} + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

where , ER = log of the employment ratio in a country i at time t , X = variable of interest, log of broadband subscription per 100 people, M = set of control variables in log terms such as fixed telephone per 100, mobile cellular per 100, population density, income and other demographics, α_i = country fixed effect, λ_t = time fixed effect.

5 Results

In this section, we present the results obtained from OLS and fixed effects model.

Table 3 presents the result obtained from the OLS regressions where the dependent variable is the ratio of employed people among the working age population(15 and older). Column (1) represents the coefficient of broadband for whole sample. Based on the OLS results, when a country goes from no broadband availability to ubiquitous availability, the employment rate of the working-age population increases by 3.02 percentage points in an average. When a low-income country moves from no broadband to full availability,

Table 3: Impact of broadband on employment:OLS

Dependent variable: log(employment rate(age 15+))

VARIABLES	(1) All	(2) Low income	(3) Middle income	(4) High income
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0302** (0.00300)	0.0322*** (0.0113)	0.0125*** (0.00359)	0.0185*** (0.00554)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.0129*** (0.00440)	0.0474*** (0.0159)	0.0162*** (0.00588)	0.0125* (0.00758)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	0.00525 (0.00440)	0.0140 (0.0120)	0.00738 (0.00521)	0.0118 (0.00952)
ln(population density)	0.00916*** (0.00305)	0.0103 (0.0168)	0.0170*** (0.00350)	0.0704** (0.00573)
ln(GDP per capita)	0.00218 (0.00197)	0.0198** (0.00824)	0.00112 (0.00247)	0.00686** (0.00348)
ln(population age 15-64)	0.0225** (0.00959)	0.0279*** (0.0311)	0.0436*** (0.0136)	0.0358** (0.0180)
ln(pop. age 65 and more)	0.0112 (0.00778)	0.0108** (0.0479)	0.0175** (0.0120)	0.0168* (0.0106)
ln(secondary)	0.0112 (0.0152)	0.0115** (0.0390)	-0.0713** (0.0222)	0.0107 (0.0245)
Constant	4.123*** (0.0508)	3.668*** (0.190)	4.137*** (0.0607)	4.192*** (0.0960)
Observations	1,628	170	913	545
R-squared	0.14	0.105	0.86	0.44

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

employment rate rise by 3.22 percentage points. The broadband coefficient for high-income countries is 0.0185 indicating that moving from no broadband to full access in high-income countries creates employment by 1.85 percentage points. Most of the developed countries consist of big cities and more urban area, and markets are better connected in comparison to low-income countries. As there are more isolated markets in low-income countries, so broadband effect is higher than high-income countries.

Table 4 presents the results obtained from the baseline fixed effects model by adding country fixed effects and uses the within-country variation over time to eliminate the unobserved heterogeneity between countries. The broadband coefficient remains statistically significant for all income level countries. Based on the results obtained from country fixed effects model, moving from no broadband to full availability, the percentage of employed people rises by 1.63 percentage points in high-income countries, while employment in low-income countries' increases by 1.71 percentage points.

We can see the magnitude of the broadband coefficients has decreased from OLS to fixed effect model, as variation within countries eliminates the spurious correlation between broadband and employment that is due to unobserved heterogeneity among the countries. As we can see from the column (1) of table 4, the coefficient of broadband is 0.0279 implying that for every 100 percentage increase in broadband availability, there is an increase working-age population employment by 2.79 percentage points in an average. Every 1 percentage increase in broadband accessibility is associated with .071 percentage points increase in employment rate in low-income countries. In middle-income countries, every 100 percentage change in broadband is associated with 2.44 percentage change in employment rate, which is higher than that for high (1.63) and low income countries(1.71) Most of the middle-income countries

Table 4: Impact of broadband on employment: fixed effects

Dependent variable: $\log(\text{employment rate}(\text{age } 15+))$

VARIABLES	(1) All	(2) Low	(3) Middle	(4) High
$\ln(\text{broadband per } 100)$	0.0279** (0.00266)	0.0171** (0.00600)	0.0244** (0.00553)	0.0163*** (0.00418)
$\ln(\text{telephone per } 100)$	0.00909 (0.0125)	0.00573 (0.0227)	0.0120 (0.0134)	0.0298 (0.0337)
$\ln(\text{mobile cellular per } 100)$	0.0122 (0.00857)	0.00231 (0.0265)	0.0222** (0.0107)	0.0103 (0.0180)
$\ln(\text{population density})$	0.651** (0.273)	0.750 (0.705)	0.500* (0.268)	1.167* (0.588)
$\ln(\text{GDP per capita})$	0.0388** (0.0172)	0.00424 (0.0676)	0.0295 (0.0188)	0.0679** (0.0319)
$\ln(\text{population age } 15\text{-}64)$	0.492** (0.241)	-1.255 (0.779)	0.352* (0.204)	0.891* (0.506)
$\ln(\text{population } 65 \text{ and more})$	0.106 (0.0738)	0.653** (0.272)	-0.0572 (0.0416)	0.296** (0.143)
$\ln(\text{secondary})$	0.0305 (0.0440)	0.0135 (0.112)	0.0248 (0.0319)	0.0237 (0.0800)
Constant	-1.687 (2.904)	13.24 (8.413)	2.309 (2.288)	-7.149 (5.741)
Observations	1,175	136	632	407
R-squared	0.029	0.192	0.082	0.038
Number of id	142	18	75	49
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

are enjoying high-income growth; this may be the cause for a high coefficient of broadband on employment.

Table 5 examines whether the rise in employment is accompanied by increase into the labor force or movements from unemployment to employment

Table 5: Fixed effects for Population , Labor force , Unemployment and Employment(full sample)

VARIABLES	(1) ln(labor 15 plus)	(2) ln(unemployed)	(3) ln(employed)
ln(broadband per 100)	4.53e-05 (0.000483)	-0.0206** (0.00424)	0.0279*** (0.00266)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.00196 (0.00243)	0.00523 (0.0208)	0.00909 (0.0117)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	0.00629*** (0.00114)	-0.0336*** (0.0102)	0.0122** (0.00618)
ln(population density)	0.0622** (0.0306)	-0.720*** (0.265)	0.651*** (0.180)
ln(GDP per capita)	0.00968*** (0.00292)	0.00745 (0.0262)	0.0388** (0.0161)
ln(population age 15-64)	0.0375 (0.0275)	0.459* (0.237)	0.492*** (0.151)
ln(population 65 and more)	0.0491*** (0.00924)	-0.0304 (0.0810)	0.106** (0.0475)
ln(secondary)	0.0468*** (0.00521)	0.0968** (0.0461)	0.0305 (0.0293)
Constant	2.625*** (0.312)	7.296*** (2.578)	-1.687 (1.707)
Observations	2,159	1,930	1,175
R-squared	0.123	0.029	0.029
Number of id	157	144	142
Country FE	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

for the full sample. The dependent variables in Columns (1) through (3) are the logarithms of the percentage of people in the labor force, the percentage of people unemployed in the country, and the percentage of employed people in the country, respectively. As expected there is no significant relationship between broadband access and number of people in labor force, which is indicated

by the broadband coefficient. Gaining full broadband access is accompanied by 2.79 percentage increase in the employment in a country. Unemployment rate in a country decreases by 2.06 percentage points as the result of broadband access. More job opportunities and lower search costs may be reasons for movements into the labor force(Atasoy 2013). This pattern of results suggests that the employment increases tend to come from people who previously lived in a different country and from people who were not already in the labor force. Table 6 examines whether the rise in employment is accompanied by changes into the labor force or movements from unemployment to employment for low-income countries. Moving from no broadband to full broadband access is not associated to the labor force in the country and close to zero. Moving to full broadband access from no broadband is accompanied with 1.17 percentage points decrease in the unemployment rate and employment rate increases by 1.71 percentage points.

Table 7 analyses whether or not the increase in employment is accompanied by changes into the labor force or movements from unemployment to employment for middle-income countries. As the magnitude of the broadband coefficients in column(1) of table 7 is minuscule, we can say broadband has no effect on labor force. Moving from no broadband to full broadband access is associated with a 0.9 percentage decrease in the unemployment rate in a

Table 6: Fixed effects for Population , Labor force , Unemployment and Employment(low income countries)

VARIABLES	ln(labor 15 plus)	ln(unemployed)	ln(employed)
ln(broadband per 100)	0.000322 (0.00183)	-0.0117** (0.0118)	0.0171*** (0.00600)
ln(telephone per 100)	-0.00684 (0.0102)	-0.0593 (0.0776)	0.00573 (0.0227)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	-0.0114* (0.00630)	-0.0279 (0.0453)	0.00231 (0.0265)
ln(population density)	-0.155*** (0.0458)	0.216 (0.646)	0.750 (0.705)
ln(GDP per capita)	0.0506*** (0.0177)	-0.230 (0.201)	0.00424 (0.0676)
ln(population age 15-64)	-0.0307 (0.0940)	0.507 (1.137)	1.255 (0.779)
ln(population age 65 and more)	0.0391 (0.0672)	0.481 (0.347)	0.653** (0.272)
ln(secondary)	-0.00126 (0.0353)	-0.0979 (0.270)	0.0135 (0.112)
Constant	3.649*** (1.266)	-8.986 (12.39)	13.24 (8.413)
Observations	284	242	136
R-squared	0.359	0.115	0.192
Number of id	23	20	18
Country FE	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

middle-income country. Moving to full broadband access is accompanied with 5.44 percentage increase in the employment rate.

Table 8 examines whether the rise in employment is accompanied by changes into the labor force or movements from unemployment to employment for the high-income countries. The dependent variables in Columns (1) through (3) are the logarithms of the percentage of people in the labor force, the number

Table 7: Fixed effects for Population , Labor force , Unemployment and Employment(Middle income countries)

VARIABLES	(1) ln(labor 15 plus)	(2) ln(unemployed)	(3) ln(employed)
ln(broadband per 100)	8.85e-05 (0.000685)	-0.00951** (0.00578)	0.0244** (0.00255)
ln(telephone per 100)	-0.0131*** (0.00359)	-0.0421 (0.0297)	0.0120 (0.0109)
ln(mobile cellular per)100	0.00150 (0.00158)	-0.0508*** (0.0139)	0.0222*** (0.00513)
ln(population density)	0.136*** (0.0514)	2.131*** (0.440)	0.500*** (0.165)
ln(GDP per capita)	-0.00333 (0.00402)	0.0604* (0.0347)	0.0295** (0.0138)
ln(population age 15-64)	-0.138*** (0.0455)	-1.095*** (0.384)	0.352*** (0.134)
ln(population age 65 and more)	0.0511*** (0.0132)	-0.135 (0.116)	-0.0572 (0.0410)
ln(secondary)	-0.0411*** (0.00851)	0.0275 (0.0732)	0.0248 (0.0275)
Constant	4.892*** (0.524)	10.81** (4.258)	2.309 (1.495)
Observations	1,155	1,037	632
R-squared	0.068	0.065	0.082
Number of id	84	77	75
Country FE	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

of people unemployed in the country, and the number of employed people in the country, respectively. We do not have evidence that the broadband access is associated with the labor force as a broadband coefficient is very small(almost zero). Gaining full broadband access is accompanied with 1.63 percentage increase in employment rate and unemployment rate decreases by .46 percentage points.

Table 8: Fixed effects for Population , Labor force , Unemployment and Employment(high income countries)

VARIABLES	(1) ln(labor 15 plus)	(2) ln(unemployed)	(3) ln(employed)
ln(broadband per 100)	-0.000319 (0.00117)	-0.00463* (0.0132)	0.0163** (0.00518)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.0250** (0.0101)	-0.138* (0.0805)	0.0298 (0.0337)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	0.0191*** (0.00529)	-0.0417 (0.0279)	0.0103 (0.0180)
ln(population density)	-0.226 (0.228)	1.404 (1.345)	1.167* (0.588)
ln(GDP per capita)	0.0292*** (0.0107)	-0.0594 (0.0697)	0.0679** (0.0319)
ln(population age 15-64)	0.169 (0.231)	-1.147 (1.112)	0.891* (0.506)
ln(population age 65 and more)	0.0819** (0.0396)	-0.0206 (0.258)	0.296** (0.143)
ln(secondary)	-0.0386* (0.0226)	0.114 (0.308)	-0.0237 (0.0800)
Constant	0.376 (2.596)	15.69 (11.93)	-7.149 (5.741)
Observations	720	651	407
R-squared	0.332	0.115	0.038
Number of id	50	47	49
Country FE	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The rise in the quantity of employed laborers can be considered for by a rise in a number of companies in the country and by raised hiring by existing companies. We employ country, and time fixed effects designs to examine the effects of broadband access on these channels. Column (1) of Table 9 presents there is a positive effect of broadband availability on the log of the number of employers. Getting broadband access is accompanied with about

4.07 percentage points rise in the number of companies in the country, and this coefficient is statistically insignificant. At the same time, broadband access is associated with 6.7 percentage points increase in the number of employee per employer. Broadband access seems to fascinate companies to a territory and to broaden the recruitment base of companies. The primary effect is due to an increase in the size of companies.

Table 9: Effects broadband on number of employers and employees per employer

VARIABLES	(1) ln(number of employers)	(2) ln(employees per employer)
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0471 (0.0318)	0.0670** (0.0314)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.744*** (0.157)	0.621*** (0.153)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	-0.0683 (0.0826)	0.0365 (0.0813)
ln(population density)	1.894 (1.823)	1.576 (1.817)
ln(GDP per capita)	-0.0910 (0.200)	-0.0673 (0.198)
ln(population age 15-64)	-2.564 (1.558)	-1.488 (1.559)
ln(population age 65 and more)	0.768 (0.609)	-0.429 (0.597)
ln(secondary)	0.590* (0.355)	0.0419 (0.358)
Constant	30.68* (16.58)	29.95* (16.83)
Observations	1,157	1,260
R-squared	0.032	0.022
Number of id	94	95
Country FE	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 10: Effect of Broadband on Employment with various Education level

VARIABLES	(1) ln(Adv. Degree)	(2) ln(Intermediate)	(3) ln(Basic Education)	(4) ln(without Basic Ed.)
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0402*** (0.0301)	0.180 (0.134)	-0.0129*** (0.185)	-0.113 (0.282)
ln(telephone per 100)	-1.166*** (0.399)	-0.485 (0.593)	0.901 (0.821)	-0.443 (1.052)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	0.544*** (0.199)	0.432 (0.296)	-1.066*** (0.411)	0.767 (0.553)
ln(population density)	0.712 (6.635)	-49.93*** (9.882)	51.59*** (13.72)	-1.843 (20.56)
ln(GDP per capita)	1.419*** (0.507)	-0.319 (0.756)	-2.625** (1.044)	0.991 (1.440)
ln(population age 15-64)	-0.845 (5.904)	29.53*** (8.790)	-24.66** (12.21)	-5.417 (18.99)
ln(population age 65 and more)	10.70*** (1.600)	8.806*** (2.381)	-18.75*** (3.293)	-5.884 (4.946)
ln(secondary)	3.310*** (0.957)	1.862 (1.425)	4.706** (1.968)	-14.70*** (2.647)
Constant	-122.8* (69.09)	-316.9*** (102.5)	561.9*** (143.4)	48.46 (215.3)
Observations	878	876	875	647
R-squared	0.556	0.123	0.225	0.071
Number of id	133	134	133	118
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The skill -biased technological innovation model explores how information technologies influence labor demand. The core prediction of that model is that if broadband technology is interdependent to labor market skills, then we should see greater effects among higher trained employees. The effect should be small for unskilled workers. In this section, we examine whether employment advantages are stronger for countries that have larger proportion of employees receiving an advanced college degree. We find evidence that conclusions are coherent with the skill-biased technological change model.

Table 10 presents the results from fixed effect regressions. Column (1) depicts that if broadband access is increased by 100 percentage points, there is

an increase in employment of workers having advanced college degree by 4.02 percentage points. The broadband coefficient is insignificant but positive in case of workers with an intermediate degree. In the case of workers only having basic education, every 100 percentage increase in broadband access decreases an employment opportunity by 1.29 percentage points. The broadband coefficient for the workers without basic education goes down by 11.3 percentage points when the broadband access increase by 100 percentage points. These results are consistent with theory that broadband adoption increases firm's demand for skilled labors but decreases the demand for unskilled workers.

Table 11: Broadband and skill interaction

VARIABLES	(1) ln(employment)	(2) ln(employment)	(3) ln(employers)	(4) ln(employers)	(5) ln(employee)	(6) ln(employee)
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0279** (0.00267)	-0.784*** (0.0805)	0.0470 (0.0319)	-0.571 (3.397)	0.0670** (3.380)	-0.025** (0.075)
ln(broadband per 100 × employed with college degree)		0.786*** (0.0806)		0.549** (3.402)		0.622** (0.086)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.0097 (0.0118)	-0.00338 (0.00659)	0.744*** (0.157)	0.746** (0.316)	0.621*** (0.161)	5.235 (6.480)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	0.0121* (0.00625)	0.0198*** (0.00474)	-0.0684 (0.0827)	-0.490** (0.221)	0.08* (8.771)	6.788 (4.545)
ln(population density)	0.641*** (0.273)	0.386*** (0.114)	1.903 (1.825)	7.598* (4.464)	18.07 (193.6)	16.2** (91.68)
ln(GDP per capita)	0.0385** (0.0162)	0.0236** (0.0102)	-0.0908 (0.200)	-0.732* (0.419)	-0.0787 (0.198)	-4.287 (8.611)
ln(population age 15-64)	0.484*** (0.152)	0.265*** (0.0917)	-2.566* (1.559)	-1.692 (3.319)	-2.94 (165.3)	160.8** (6.15)
ln(population age 65 and more)	0.105** (0.0478)	0.0347 (0.0284)	0.766 (0.610)	3.325*** (1.133)	-2.60 (4.68)	9.44*** (23.27)
ln(secondary)	0.0296 (0.0295)	-0.0201 (0.0187)	0.593* (0.356)	0.646 (0.968)	0.0418** (0.72)	2.71** (1.88)
Constant	-1.606 (1.723)	-2.100* (1.069)	30.71* (16.59)	50.27 (40.75)	19 (1,760)	-494.4 (836.8)
Observations	1,169	714	1,156	407	1,156	407
R-squared	0.028	0.201	0.032	0.122	0.011	0.100
Number of countries	142	98	94	54	94	54
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Here in table 11, we examine whether or not the countries that have a more skilled labor force attain larger employment with broadband expansion. Table shows the results obtained from the fixed effect regressions that have interaction between log of broadband per hundred and percentage of people employed with advanced education. In columns (1) and (2), the dependent variable is the log of a fraction of people employed with a college degree. Column (1) is the results of baseline fixed effect model. In column (2), we include the interaction term between broadband per hundred and fraction of people employed with a college degree. The coefficient for the interaction term is 0.78 which is significantly different from zero. This shows that the effect of broadband is higher on countries with higher percentage of people employed with college degree.

In column (4) and (6) of table 10, we investigate whether or not there are differential effects on the number of employers and employees per employer based on the skill composition of the country. There is the statically significant effect of broadband access to the number of employers and employees per employers. The coefficient of the interaction term is positive and significant indicating that if there is a higher number of collage graduates in the labor force its likely to get more affected by broadband availability.

Another approach to examine the skill-biased technological changes hy-

pothesis is to analyze differential effects on various jobs. As various jobs has various skill compositions and local demand dependence, they are expected to be affected deferentially by broadband expansion. Table 11 presents the broadband coefficients for various jobs from models that include time and country fixed effects. Column (1) uses percentage of people working as managers as dependent variable. Managers are people with advanced education and perform abstract tasks. The broadband coefficient in this case is statistically significant and positive indicating that broadband plays significant role to increase the employment for the managers.

Table 12: Effect of Broadband on various professions

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
	managers	professionals	clerical	technicians	service	skilled agri	craft workers	machine operators	armed force
ln(broadband per 100)	0.110** (0.113)	0.0248*** (0.206)	0.0481 (0.149)	0.285** (0.114)	-0.0179 (0.164)	-0.571 (0.519)	0.200 (0.130)	0.266** (0.103)	0.000441 (0.0443)
ln(telephone per 100)	1.066** (0.467)	0.170 (0.840)	0.803 (0.655)	0.300 (0.472)	2.484*** (0.679)	1.871 (2.142)	0.176 (0.527)	0.722* (0.0437)	0.402** (0.0184)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	0.543* (0.298)	0.895* (0.536)	0.334 (0.392)	0.201 (0.301)	0.345 (0.433)	-1.235 (1.377)	0.679** (0.337)	-0.0940 (0.271)	-0.0370 (0.143)
ln(population density)	29.66*** (8.127)	65.69*** (14.64)	65.15*** (10.70)	36.70*** (8.224)	2.193 (11.82)	132.3*** (38.03)	20.57** (9.217)	14.62** (7.387)	5.221 (3.257)
ln(GDP per capita)	0.875 (0.717)	1.471 (1.294)	2.860*** (0.942)	2.216*** (0.725)	0.594 (1.042)	7.740** (3.301)	1.222 (0.812)	1.721*** (0.651)	0.301 (0.287)
ln(population age 15-64)	19.56*** (6.960)	52.42*** (12.51)	62.11*** (9.159)	37.51*** (7.042)	1.136 (10.12)	131.8*** (32.42)	13.22* (7.865)	-9.842 (6.329)	-7.220*** (2.728)
ln(population age 65more)	4.810** (1.865)	2.894 (3.339)	1.099 (2.447)	0.427 (1.887)	-7.441*** (2.712)	-8.080 (8.622)	-0.557 (2.098)	6.030*** (1.695)	1.071 (0.715)
ln(secondary)	0.482 (1.153)	1.485 (2.069)	0.726 (1.517)	1.003 (1.166)	0.822 (1.676)	-2.172 (5.314)	-3.903*** (1.300)	1.472 (1.056)	0.975* (0.503)
Constant	-204.1*** (68.76)	-502.8*** (124.0)	-601.9*** (90.50)	-354.1*** (69.64)	80.67 (100.1)	1.354*** (319.4)	81.47 (78.00)	69.28 (62.55)	72.76** (28.49)
Observations	459	457	461	461	461	446	456	459	293
R-squared	0.090	0.078	0.138	0.129	0.051	0.094	0.066	0.102	0.089
Number of id	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

6 Evidence on the Causality

Endogeneity is a serious complication in investigating the relationship between broadband technology and the employment rate. Since broadband is not distributed randomly across countries, the broadband variable in the baseline model is likely to be positively correlated with the error term and therefore, results in a biased estimate of the causal effect of broadband on labor market outcomes. The estimates presented so far control for an exceptionally wide variety of possible con-founders and alleviate concerns about an omitted variable bias. Country fixed effect control for all aspects, observable and unobservable, that are fixed over time. This model describes the association between broadband and employment outcomes by the variation in results over time, in the same country. Time fixed effects control for all national trends in employment and broadband access. So, for example, we can control for the possibility that a secular increase in wages and broadband access is stimulated by totally unrelated things or operated by a simple causal effect of wages on broadband access.

Additionally, we control for observable county characteristics that might be interacted with both variations in broadband and employment market results that differ by each country. We run regressions that have leads and lag of broadband per 100 and the employment ratio to determine whether or

Table 13: Lags and Leads 1

Dependent variable: Employment Rate	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Lag 1 Employment Rate	0.463*** (0.103)	0.462*** (0.104)	0.421*** (0.105)	0.424*** (0.103)
Lag 2 Employment Rate	0.162** (0.0775)	0.161** (0.0761)	0.143* (0.0736)	0.146* (0.0760)
Broadband per 100	0.0721*** (0.00133)	0.0204*** (0.00240)	0.0343*** (0.00311)	0.0106*** (0.00156)
Lag 1 Broadband per 100		0.0225** (0.00206)	0.0360** (0.00255)	
Lag 2 Broadband per 100		0.0904* (0.00203)	0.0138* (0.00219)	
Lead 1 Broadband per 100			5.57e-10 (3.02e-09)	8.37e-10 (3.12e-09)
Constant	20.72*** (3.342)	20.90*** (3.427)	24.15*** (3.869)	23.80*** (3.764)
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	1,270	1,270	1,085	1,085
R-squared	0.381	0.382	0.318	0.315
Number of countries	108	108	106	106

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

not employment today is corresponded with broadband in the future. These tests are the essence of a Granger- causality test, which is prevalent causality between two variables in a time-series situation(Granger 1969). The results demonstrate that the direction is from broadband access to the employment rate not vice-versa.

Table 13 presents results obtained from country and time fixed effect regressions in which dependent variable is the employment rate of age 15 and more. The independent variables are leads and lag of employment rate and broadband per 100 people. The number of lags are determined by employing

Table 14: Lags and Leads 2

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Dependent variable: Broadband per 100 people				
Lag 1 Broadband per 100	0.837*** (0.0538)	0.820*** (0.0597)	0.789*** (0.0617)	0.790*** (0.0590)
Lag 2 Broadband per 100	0.0345*** (0.00915)	0.0293*** (0.00104)	0.0376*** (0.00105)	0.0540*** (0.00102)
Lag 3 Broadband per 100	-0.0795 (0.0533)	-0.0654 (0.0584)	-0.0552 (0.0590)	-0.0719 (0.0587)
Employment Rate	0.0171* (0.00905)	0.0144** (0.0204)	0.0696** (0.0209)	0.0740* (0.0130)
Lag 1 Employment rate		0.0274 (0.0190)	0.0382 (0.0249)	
Lag 2 Employment rate		-0.00662 (0.0256)	-0.00229 (0.0302)	
Lead 1 Employment rate			-0.0109 (0.0269)	-0.00895 (0.0245)
Constant	-0.502 (0.656)	0.144 (2.408)	-0.494 (3.012)	0.628 (1.568)
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Observations	1,511	1,207	1,079	1,216
R-squared	0.837	0.830	0.822	0.825
Number of countries	162	108	99	120

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

t-tests of lagged values of a dependent variable. Column (1) includes broadband as an independent variable as well as two lag of the employment rate variable that are significant according to individual t-tests. Once we identify the collection of significant lagged values of the dependent variable, we augment the regression by lagged values of the independent variable. Column (2) includes two lags of broadband variables, and column (3) incorporates the lead of the broadband variable. In both columns, the lags of broadband variable are significant, supporting lack of reverse causality. The lead of the broadband is significant, which further supports the causation we got. Column (4)

removes the lags of broadband variables to look at the robustness of the lead broadband coefficient. The coefficient of lead of broadband variable is almost same in both the cases making our assumption of lack of reverse causality more stronger.

Table 14 is analogous to Table 13 but in this instance, the conditional variable is broadband per hundred. Broadband is regressed on leads and lags of both variables controlling a county and time fixed effects design. The lags in the employment rate are not significant in columns (2) and (3). The lead of employment is insignificant in column (3), but it becomes significant once the lags of broadband variables are excluded, which is further illustrated that employment is not causing broadband expansion.

7 Conclusion

Broadband plays an important role in different sectors of the economy. Most of the governments are subsidizing the broadband dispersion. We employ data from the development indicator of the World Bank and International Labor Organization(ILO) statistics to quantify the relationship between broadband access and employment across the countries. We exploit the panel structure of the data set to eliminate permanent heterogeneity at the country level. We regressed broadband per hundred people at the employment rate

using country and time fixed effects. We find significant effects of broadband on employment: moving from no broadband to full availability increases employment rate by 3.02 percentage points in an average. Broadband increases employment rate in low-income countries by 3.22 percentage points and by 1.85 percentage points in high income countries. The employment effect is higher in low-income countries as there are more rural and isolated markets.

Broadband technology is a complement to skilled labor, and it increases the demand for educated labors. We found evidence that workers with an advanced degree are one who gets the benefit of broadband deployment, and broadband reduces the employment of workers with basic education. The results of this paper indicate that not all education level workers benefit from broadband deployment. Workers with advanced education get increased employment but employment for labor with basic education decreases, yet there is net small but positive. The employment effects are bigger for occupations that require advanced education.

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